

Exploratory Data Analysis for Investigating a Second-Hand Mobile Phone Dataset from Sri Lanka

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Abstract:- The second-hand mobile phone market attracts a lot of attention in countries with high mobile phone prices. Also, Big data and high-performance computing technologies have evolved to open new possibilities for predictive analytics. The proposed study aims to identify the patterns and trends in prices for the second-hand mobile phone market in Sri Lanka. This paper will discuss the importance of this topic, and this will provide some valuable insights about the selected dataset. To analyse, the suggested method uses a dataset of mobile phone advertising data from a Sri Lankan online sales platform. This approach will use Python, Excel and other data processing tools to handle the data in such a way that we are able to identify some interesting patterns in the data. In this analysis, we will be investigating various aspects of the dataset, such as the distribution of prices, the most popular brands, and any trends or patterns that may be present. By the end of this analysis, we hope to gain a better understanding of the used mobile phone market in Sri Lanka and identify any potential opportunities or areas for further research. This study tries to provide the steps taken while preprocessing and how plots were made to see the key features and the variation of prices of smartphones in the past this study will lead towards on making a model that can predict the optimum price for a used smartphone on the second-hand market. The suggested approach for EDA can be applied to any other dataset with minor tweaks and might be helpful in generating descriptive statistics.

Keywords:- Mobile Phones, Sri Lanka, Data Cleaning, Exploratory Data Analysis, Second-Hand.

I. INTRODUCTION

In simple terms, A mobile phone is a portable electronic device that is used for communication and can send and receive phone calls, text messages, and other types of communication over a network of cell towers. Most modern mobile phones also have a variety of additional features, such as internet access, cameras, GPS, and the ability to run apps. Mobile phones are often called "cell phones" or "cellular phones" because they use a network of cells, each with its own transmitter and receiver, to provide coverage over a large area.

Mobile phones are the most useful and advanced of all the basic and advanced ways to communicate. Mobile phones have ended up being a completely fundamental commodity in

human life. Nowadays, the world has ended up being a town with no boundaries for communication between nations and individuals.

When it comes to the major mobile phone manufacturers, Apple, Huawei, Lenovo, Samsung, Motorola, Google, Oppo, and OnePlus are some of the main producers of smartphone hardware [1].

Sellers have begun offering smartphones on several levels or at varying costs. Smartphones that are considered "flagship" or "premium" are getting more expensive, and most of them now cost between \$800 and \$1,000. Upper- and mid-range smartphones will cost between \$500 and \$700 [3], while budget phones are available below this markup. OEMs (original equipment manufacturers) of mobile phones often sell different versions of their devices that fit into one or both of these categories.

Data pre-processing, Feature Engineering, and the many stages of Exploratory Data Analysis are discussed in this paper since they are crucial to any research analysis. Primitive activities following data collection include data pre-processing, Feature Engineering, and EDA. However, these methods are not restricted to those in which data is only viewed, plotted, and modified, with no assumptions, in order to evaluate data quality and construct models. Integration of data, analysis of data, cleansing of data, the transformation of data, and dimensionality reduction are all examples of what are known as "data pre-processing" [5] [8].

When raw data is cleaned and organised, a process known as "data preparation" can begin, paving the way for feature engineering. Feature Engineering encompasses a wide range of data engineering methods, including but not limited to: encoding the data, dealing with missing data, dealing with categorical variables, etc. When it comes to the success or failure of a model. In this research, we will investigate the dataset, tools, and procedures employed in carrying out the aforementioned tasks.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

When it comes to the usage of mobile phones, according to Allyssa [1], smartphones play a crucial role in people's lives in the modern day. are considered, including the display, camera, processor, memory, screen size, battery capacity, and others. There are many things to think about when buying a

smartphone, such as a screen, camera, processor, memory, screen size, battery capacity, and so on.

In recent years, mobile phones have gotten thinner and lighter, and they now come with a wide range of extra features, such as a touch screen, camera, fingerprint sensor, 4G and 5G connectivity, a battery that can last for a long time, GPS (global positioning system), Bluetooth, NFC (near-field communication), and so on. Therefore, mobile phones have developed into a remarkable innovation known as a smartphone, thanks to the inclusion of these characteristics.

When we look at different mobile phone brands, models and prices, there is a wide variation to be seen. The iOS (iPhone operating system) and the iPhone were created by Apple [2]. If we take a look at the iPhone 13 lineup. The iPhone 13's initial price of \$799 places it in the upper or mid-range of smartphones because it makes some technical concessions, such as using an LCD (liquid crystal display) panel rather than an OLED (organic light-emitting diode) one. Apple's top device then was the 13 Pro Max, which cost \$1,199. The Pro Max is a substantially larger version of the 13 Pro. Apple continues to sell the iPhone XR and 13 small, both of which are priced within the range of entry-level smartphones. The Android operating system is supported by a lot of OEMs, and smartphones that use it are called "Android devices" in general. Google, a different manufacturer of smartphones, promotes its Pixel line. The Pixel range currently includes the Pixel 6 and Pixel 6a. The Pixel 6 is currently Google's top-selling smartphone, while the Pixel 6a is the company's \$449 entry-level model. There is also a larger "Pro" version for both the Pixel 6 and 6a [2].

Samsung's Galaxy S and Note series are two distinct and popular smartphone models [2]. For instance, the Galaxy S22, which costs \$900 and comes in a larger version called the S22 Ultra, is currently the top model in the S series. Additionally, Asus sells smartphones under the ROG and Zen models; Redmi sells smartphones under the Note and K series; and Huawei sells smartphones under the Mate and P series. The leading, cheap, midrange, and "Plus" smartphones are all made by many different companies using the same basic ideas [2].

Also, it can be seen that for mobile phones the colour, packaging, accessories in the box, and Charging cable length, these kinds of features affect very less on the price of the mobile phone [3]. But some features, such as camera quality, screen size, display type, refresh rate, operating system, RAM (random access memory), ROM (read-only memory), etc., will be affecting the price of the mobile phone immensely. This will provide a guideline for the selection of features for training the models. But consumers know the brand and model they need to purchase when it comes to these important features. For example, people who need good camera quality prefer to buy an iPhone rather than an Android phone. Also, a person who prefers more customization options will prefer a Samsung or a Redmi mobile phone. The basis of feature selection was not highlighted in the previously studied work, and this could be a point to consider when performing statistical analysis on the dataset. A visualisation of how each

feature affects the price of a mobile phone can be done using some tools like Excel, PowerBI, or Tableau.

Many research topics were found to be related to house prices and used car prices [4] [7]. But mobile price prediction was a less discussed topic. Also, the previous research was done at a time when there was no significant increase in the rate of inflation. The use of mobile phones was widely discussed, and the increase in usage was also visible. Especially when it comes to the used mobile phone market in Sri Lanka, there was not much prior work related to the topic. But there are enough sources to get the data. Therefore, carrying out exploratory data analysis on such a dataset is quite important.

III. DATA COLLECTION

A suitable dataset that was available on Kaggle[6] will be used, which contains enough data for performing predictions. The data has been collected over the course of the year 2021 from a large number of advertisements from different sellers. This has over 50,000 different records of data relevant to different mobile phones on sale. An overview of the dataset will be given under the methodology section. After the initial data preprocessing, steps can be taken to train different models, and the best ones will be selected based on their performance. Steps will be taken to decide on the selection procedure and performance measuring techniques.

IV. WORKFLOW

Fig 1. Workflow diagram

The collection of data, the initial step, will be the starting point for the final model. With a suitable dataset, we can clean the dataset and determine its suitability. Structuring and pre-processing steps will take a considerable amount of time. Exploratory data analysis will be performed to identify the patterns and trends in the dataset. This will give a clear idea about the dataset and the data points that it contains. Going further, we can visualise the data using different variables that are available to get some insights about it. The plots and the correlation maps will be useful for obtaining different patterns and then also the final dataset can be used for further analysis or prediction work.

A. Original Dataset

Fig 2. Mobile prices dataset overview

The summary for the selected dataset looks as given above (Fig 2). This dataset [6] has the prices for 2021 mobile phones that were advertised on ikman.lk, which is a well-known platform. Data has been collected over the course of the year, and the author is also adding new data. The dataset contains 51223 records, which will be sufficient for our project.

Each column contains details about each second-hand mobile phone advertisement, including brand, model, and price. Data cleansing will initially remove extraneous columns and select relevant data. After cleaning, the dataset will be much neater, leaving price and other significant parameters for further processing.

B. Approach Taken

In the first part of the study, we identified a suitable dataset that has the maximum possible data relevant to the used mobile phones in Sri Lanka. Firstly, cleaning the dataset needs to be done. The data has been collected through web scraping from ikman.lk, which is the largest online reselling platform. A large amount of data is there (more than 50000 rows). After removing null values and redundant data, we will have to deal with missing values where we cannot make use of them. For missing data, either the records will have to be deleted or they can be filled using different methods available in Python. After this preliminary data cleaning and analysis, we might still end up with 40033 records, which will be more than enough to train a model. A statistical analysis will be done in order to see the correlation between various factors and the distribution of the data. Also, from this step, we can identify various other important visualisations of characteristics in the dataset.

Next, we will discuss the approach taken by considering the knowledge gathered from the literature review. After going through several previous works, we have gathered enough knowledge to handle the dataset and move towards the model training tasks. The details about the original dataset that was selected are given, and then the proposed approach is discussed with the currently adopted methods. Thereafter, the

technologies used so far are discussed, and the other requirements are discussed in detail.

C. Conceptual Framework

Fig 3. Presentation of variables considered in the study.

D. Technology Consideration

Initially, we had to deal with the raw dataset, which is in MS Excel format. Therefore, Excel was used for handling the dataset. The Office 365 package provides all the software, including Excel to handle data. Excel can also convert the data into CSV (comma-separated values) format. The CSV format is ideal for data science and machine learning-related work. The tool used to clean data might depend on the situation. In the cases where Excel alone was not sufficient, it was decided to use Python with pandas and the NumPy libraries.

For data visualisation, Python is a good language to use because of the availability of libraries such as Numpy, Pandas, Matplotlib, and Seaborn. For Python coding, Jupyter notebooks are used, which are provided with Anaconda. Also, the Seaborn library was helpful in generating heatmaps. In the latter part of the process, we will have to continuously deal with Python and Matplotlib library where several plots are generated as needed. Depending on the situation, additional libraries will be imported and used.

V. DATA PREPROCESSING

In this section, we will be discussing the data preprocessing steps and the preliminary data analysis performed on the dataset. The objective is to ensure the data is clean and can actually support the performance and accuracy of the models that are going to be used in future. As mentioned previously, this dataset was obtained from Kaggle. This dataset [6] was found to be appropriate for our purpose of data analysis and also later we can use it for the prediction of prices when the specifications are given. We have data from Sri Lanka and a lot of used mobile phone data was there to be seen. All of the information about mobile phones came from ikman.lk, which is a website where people in Sri Lanka can buy and sell things. The dataset also has information about the seller and information that has been made public, which may not be directly needed for our work. But it is seen that the data extraction done by the owner of the dataset is almost complete and has covered many data points.

The original dataset contained columns such as brand, condition, description, edition, features, etc. It had 51223 rows and 14 columns of information, including ads for both new

and used cell phones. A summary of this dataset (Fig 2) was added in the previous section where we discussed the original dataset. All the columns were listed in it, and then it was used for further processing.

The dataset was loaded into MS Excel, which is the most common tool for data handling, and then the data was formatted as a table. This will make it easier to work with the data, and filtering is possible. As the initial step, the records that contained the new mobile phone data were removed. Since the study is considering only the domain of second-hand mobile phones, it will not be suitable to keep the new mobile phone data in the dataset. After removing all the new mobile phone records, the dataset was reduced to 49,875 rows. This means that the dataset didn't have as many records about new phones as it did about used ones. Still, we are left with more than 49,000 records.

The next task was to separate out the features that are required from the available columns in the dataset. Brand, model, and price were available in separate columns, but other important features such as RAM, ROM, 4G, or 5G were available under the description column. The extraction of such data from a single column was a bit of a tedious task. Initially, it was decided to use Excel for this, and it was seen to be successful since Excel now has some advanced features such as text and number-based filtering. From the Description column, we took out features like ROM, RAM, screen size, Dual SIM (subscriber identity module), Expandable Memory, 5G Capability, and Fingerprint Sensor. New columns were created for these data. The brand and model were available in text format. ROM value is the available inbuilt memory space in the mobile phones and its value is given in Gigabytes. Also, the RAM values are in gigabytes. The screen size is given in inches for each mobile. Then the other features are the availability of dual SIM, expandable memory, 5G, and a fingerprint sensor. A mobile phone may or may not have all these features. Therefore, based on the description, the rows were filled with "yes" or "no." And last, the price of the mobile phone is given in LKR (Sri Lankan rupees).

Handling a dataset with more than 40,000 rows is not easy, as it takes up a huge amount of RAM to load it. The other columns, like subtitle, seller name, and location, were dropped as they were not needed. Also, this helped reduce the memory size taken up by the dataset while working with it. Rows with insufficient features were removed. If any major factor, like the model, price, or RAM, is missing, those records cannot be used for further data processing. An operating system column was added using a reference table since it was easy to identify the models that use Android, iOS, Symbian, and other operating systems. The screen size was not available for most of the devices. Therefore, a separate table was created as a reference table with the screen size, and the VLOOKUP function with the MATCH function was used to fill the main data set using the reference table.

A. Duplicate and Low variation data

Having duplicate data will not be useful for price prediction. Data about the same mobile phone advertisement might appear in several places with the same price. All

duplicate values were selected and removed. Excel had a useful feature for this under conditional formatting tools to select and delete the duplicates. This made the task easier, so it was easier to handle the duplicate data without going through each and every record.

Now, the dataset has 41960 rows, and the ones with low variation and not enough data were picked out and removed. The rows that have missing values in several columns cannot be used further for the study. After that, the unique brand values were listed with the respective number of occurrences. So we were able to see the number of records available from each brand. Surprisingly, there were 38 models to be seen, and the unknown brands were labelled as "Other brand." In the below table, the brands in red don't have enough data points for training a model. Therefore, they were removed and the major brands were kept. The total number of unique brands was 18 after filtering, and the total number of unique models was 621. The brands kept are ['Apple', 'Samsung', 'Huawei', 'Xiaomi', 'Sony', 'Oppo', 'Nokia', 'Vivo', 'LG', 'OnePlus', 'Realme', 'Google', 'Infinix', 'HTC', 'Asus', 'Greentel', 'Blackberry', 'ZTE']

B. Incorrect and Irrelevant data

Brand	Occurrences
Huawei	3027
Apple	18751
Samsung	8716
Xiaomi	2941
Greentel	14
Nokia	640
LG	561
Sony	2301
Oppo	1264
HTC	61
BlackBerry	17
Vivo	797
Asus	17
Google	147
Infinix	114
OnePlus	342
Realme	315
Total	40025

Fig 4. Brand vs. Occurrences (after removing incorrect data).

This was a crucial step where the irrelevant data was selected and removed. While filtering and observing all the brands, there were some mismatches. Eg: Nokia mobiles had the wrong brand name, "Lumia," which belongs to Microsoft. Because the basic knowledge of mobile phones was present, it was simple to identify incorrect data, and it was also possible to detect and correct these errors. In the worst cases, the rows were removed. After this step, we found all the unique brand names and the number of occurrences in the latest set of data. It is now down to 40,023 records. The total number of unique brands was 17 after filtering, and the total number of unique models was 600.

C. Handling missing values

Using Python, the blank cells were filled using the interpolate method by assuming the values to be equal to the nearest neighbouring values. Since the data was put in order from least expensive to most expensive, the ROM values tend to go up as the price goes up. As a result, we can assume that the interpolate function using the nearest method would do a good job in this case.

```
(df.isnull().sum()/df.shape[0]*100)[df.isnull().sum(>0]
ROM 34.542638
dtype: float64

Observation
ROM column contains 13896 missing values. So these have to be filled using a suitable method.

df = df.interpolate(method='nearest', limit_direction='forward')
```

Fig 5. Using the interpolate method to fill missing values.

The above method was used on the dataset, and it will find the missing values and fill them in automatically. The direction used is forward since we can see that the first few rows already have values.

D. Handling categorical data

The next task was to handle the categorical data. Yes or No variables were converted into binary values since Python will easily handle numerical values rather than text data. Also, values should be assigned to the brand and model columns. The values for four categorical variables other than the model and brand are replaced with 0s and 1s. The below output shows the changes after using the replace method in Pandas.

```
In [11]: df["Dual Sim"] = df["Dual Sim"].replace(["Yes","No"],[1,0])
df["Expandable Memory"] = df["Expandable Memory"].replace(["Yes","No"],[1,0])
df["5G"] = df["5G"].replace(["Yes","No"],[1,0])
df["Fingerprint Sensor"] = df["Fingerprint Sensor"].replace(["Yes","No"],[1,0])

In [40]: df.head()

Out[40]:
```

	Brand	Model	ROM	RAM	OS	Screen size	Dual Sim	Expandable Memory	5G	Fingerprint Sensor	Price
0	Huawei	Y5 Prime	16.0	2.0	Android	5.5	1	1	0	1	5000
1	Huawei	Y5	16.0	2.0	Android	5.7	1	1	0	1	5000
2	Apple	iPhone 4S	16.0	1.0	iOS	3.5	0	0	0	0	5000
3	Huawei	Y5	16.0	2.0	Android	5.7	0	0	0	0	5000
4	Huawei	Y5	16.0	2.0	Android	5.7	1	0	0	0	5000

Fig 6. Summary of the dataset after replacing values.

VI. EXPLORATORY DATA ANALYSIS

After the initial data cleaning steps, an EDA (exploratory data analysis) was performed. The steps you would take to find out more about something before buying a mobile phone are similar to the steps that data scientists call "exploratory data analysis." The process of looking at data for the first time to uncover patterns, find outliers, test hypotheses, and check assumptions using summary statistics and graphical representations is an important part of exploratory data analysis.

It is better to first understand the data and then try to learn as much as possible from it. Therefore, we have done an EDA before messing around with the data to see what insights we can gain from the dataset that we have and what needs to be corrected before putting them into the training algorithms.

VII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We used the Matplotlib and Seaborn libraries to plot various charts and extract important insights from them. One such graph is shown above, which shows the average price of mobile phones under each brand. We can see that the Oneplus and Apple brands are on top with the highest average price, and the least price seen. Several types of graphs can be plotted while performing the data preprocessing steps. From here onwards, the study will be carried out further, along with the exploratory data analysis. The graphs and their detailed observations will be discussed in the next few sections. This will be the initial step taken before training different models and making predictions using any dataset.

A univariate analysis was done initially to see the available brands and their count. The below graph was obtained when the 'Brands' column was plotted with its count. It is observed that 'Apple' is the brand with the majority of mobile phone advertisements in our dataset. Apple is known to have a good second-hand market value and it is reflected in our dataset too. Second, comes Samsung which is another popular brand and thereafter all other brands have recorded less than 2500. We can expect a higher accuracy for Apple phones since it has a large number of data in our dataset.

Fig 7. Available brands vs count graph.

Another graph was plotted to see the price distribution (Fig 8). It was not a perfect bell shape; rather, it was skewed to the right. Therefore, we can say that a large number of mobile phones are priced below Rs. 100,000, and very few mobile phones have a higher price tag. This skewness may have an impact on the accuracy of linear regression results but it might work for other regression algorithms. Since, we discuss here only about the analysis part here we will not go into details about the further procedures. Models of the mobile phones were not plotted because there are more than 600 variations in the models. Therefore, it will not be easy to analyse that many models using a graph.

Fig 8. Seaborn plot for price distribution.

Fig 10. Plot for RAM vs Price.

Fig 9. Plot for screen size vs price.

Fig 11. Plot for ROM vs Price.

The above graph is plotted to see the variation of prices along with the different screen sizes. A gradual rise in the data point is seen in the above plot. Therefore, we can say that the price is increasing with the size of the mobile phone. But this cannot be clearly justified, and we can confirm this by generating a heatmap.

Similarly, a scatter plot was taken for other parameters. The RAM vs. Price graph is shown below, and these are the observations made using it. A higher variation is seen for the 6GB variants. There are mobile phones with a wide price range which are having 6GB of RAM capacity. Then the lowest prices are seen among the feature phones which have less than 500MB of RAM. The highest capacity available is 12GB in our dataset and generally, they should be more expensive than the other mobile phones. But the trends seen in our dataset will not justify that statement and we will have to consider other features as well to decide the variation of prices.

Fig 11 shows the plot for ROM vs Price. And the observations made are: A few variations exist for the ROM capacities. The feature phones will have less memory space and smartphones will have ROM even up to 1TB. Therefore according to the dataset There are many phones with ROM in between the range of 0 to 64GB and also with some outliers.

Fig 12. Plot for operating system vs price.

In the above plot, we can see that only 5 categories are present for Operating systems. The two most popular types are Android and iOS, as observed from the graph. There are other operating system types which are less popular, mainly the operating systems that come with the feature phones. Those ones are separately categorised under other operating systems.

Barplots were taken for the parameters, which have binary values. All these features are plotted against their average prices. For example, the availability of the dual SIM feature. As plotting features, we considered dual sim, 5G, expandable memory, and fingerprint sensor. All these features have either “Yes” or “No” values. Therefore it was easier to convert these categorical data by replacing them with 1’s or 0’s.

Fig 13. Plots for mean values of categorical variables.

As observed from the above graphs, many mobile phones support the 5G feature. Since 5G support came recently to mobile phones but still it is there to be seen in the used mobile phones which were advertised. A reason for this might be the unavailability of many 5G phones in the dataset. Considering the mean value of prices, in this case, would give us a better idea. Prices for mobile phones without 5G can reach Rs. 600,000. There must be outliers, about which we will have to take care later.

A similar variation of prices is to be seen for the dual-SIM and single-SIM mobile phones. Many mobile phones don't support dual SIMs, expandable memory, or a fingerprint sensor. Equal distributions show that having an expandable memory or an extra slot for memory cards doesn't make a big difference in the prices. As we saw earlier, most mobile phones are from the Apple brand, so we can assume that the results seen in the below graphs are more biased towards the features of Apple phones. The average price for a mobile phone without expandable memory is high. This is also possible due to the fact that many new mobile phones have removed the extra memory slot and increased the internal memory capacity. Also, the average price for mobile phones without a fingerprint sensor is high compared to mobile phones with it. This is possible due to the other authentication

methods, such as faceId which Apple provides. And also the feature phones don't have most of these features.

The above graph shows the availability of the Dual Sim feature for each individual brand of mobile phone in our dataset. The orange colour shows the availability of this feature, while the blue colour shows the unavailability. This stacked bar graph is really useful in showing us multiple features for a single brand. When examined we can see that Apple, Blackberry, Google, LG aLG, Sony has only few phones supporting Dual sim feature. And the rest of the brands have a considerably high amount of mobile phones which support Dual sims.

Fig 14. Stacked bar plot for dual SIM vs. brand.

Fig 15. Heatmap for all variables in the dataset.

Finally, we have produced a heatmap of all the features available. All the columns were considered and using the seaborn library, we were able to generate the above-shown heatmap. As the observations show, A few variations exist for the RAM capacities.

The feature phones will have less RAM (less than 1 GB) and smartphones will have RAM even up to 12 GB. Therefore according to the dataset, there are many phones with RAM in the range of 0 to 6 GB and also with some outliers. A positive correlation is represented by dark tones, whereas negative correlation is represented by lighter shades. We can see numbers indicating how features in grid cells are associated with one another since we have set annot=True.

We can deduce from this that "ROM", "RAM," and "Screen size" correlates positively with "Price" while negatively with "Dual Sim", "Expandable Memory" and "Fingerprint Sensor". There is essentially no relationship between "5G" and "Price".

VIII. CONCLUSION

Data Correlation could be because many variables or attributes of the dataset are linked or depend on each other. We can learn some things with the help of correlation. One or more characteristics depend on another characteristic or a reason for another characteristic.

Positive Correlation: This means that if a feature X goes down, feature Y goes down as well, or if a feature Y goes up, feature X goes up as well. Both things move in the same direction, and there is a straight line between them.

Negative Correlation: If feature X goes down, feature Y must go up, and vice versa.

No Correlation: These two things don't have anything in common.

The dataset used was huge and initially had over 50000 data points. We cannot go through each and every row in such a big dataset. But with modern-day technologies such as Python and related libraries, it is possible to load a big dataset and manipulate it. Pandas and Numpy are such useful libraries to perform such operations. By removing redundant data, and invalid data and filling in missing values we cleaned the dataset. The code used was provided in the figures as well. Then the plots were made using the Matplotlib library and it gave a clear view of the arrangement of data points within our dataset. We identified the skewness of the price and this might lead to inaccurate results if the price was predicted using other variables. Especially linear regression will not be suitable here. Other types of regression algorithms which can handle multicollinearity will produce reasonably accurate results. There were no highly correlated variables or highly negative correlations to be seen.

FUTURE WORK

The data preprocessing part improves data understanding and removes irregularities and unnecessary values. This will help to prepare data for analysis as mentioned above. And with an exploratory data analysis we can identify the hidden patterns in the dataset, and we can use machine learning models to do various predictions. Further, this will improve accuracy and also helps in machine learning model selection.

We have provided a cleaned dataset with EDA results. Using them we can identify the columns or the specifications of mobile phones which greatly affect the price. By removing or adding columns with other specifications related to mobile phones (such as Operating system, and battery capacity) a regression problem can be developed where the price can be predicted for any given specification. This dataset can be

extended by adding recent data points since this contains data mostly from the year 2021. For anybody who is interested in analysing data, the above-shown methodology will be useful to carry out their own research work. The preliminary steps remain almost the same for any dataset which is being used for a study.

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